

**D3.1 Review of the state of the art on use cases
in sub-TH/THz technologies in 6G for XR
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**Applications of 6G sub-THz/THz technologies to support
future XR services**

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3. Acronyms

ADC	Analog-to-digital converter
AOA	Angle of arrival
AP	Access Point
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
C&R	Communications and radar
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CP-OFDM	Cyclic Prefix OFDM
CSI	Channel State Information
CW	Continuous Wave
DAC	Digital-to-analog converter
DE-MS-QP	Data-Embedded Multi-Subband Quasi-Perfect
DFE	Digital Front-End
DL	Downlink
GSPS	Giga-Samples Per Second
ICI	Inter-carrier interference
IF	Intermediate frequency
IoT	Internet of Things
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
LNA	Low-noise amplifier
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LPDC	Low-Density Parity Check
MAC	Medium Access Control
MC	Multi-carrier
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
OAI	OpenAirInterface
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
PA	Power amplifier
PAPR	Peak-to-average power ratio
PHY	Physical Layer
RF	Radio Frequency
RFSoc	Radio Frequency System on Chip
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SC	Single-carrier
SC-FDE	Single Carrier with Frequency Domain Equalization
SC-FDM	Single-Carrier Frequency Division Multiplexing
SD-FEC	Soft-Decision Forward Error Correction
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SE	Spectral Efficiency
SISO	Single Input Single Output
SoCs	System-on-Chips
UL	Uplink
VDI	Virginia Diodes
VNA	Vector Network analyser
VSA	Vector Signal Analysis

4. Introduction

In the realm of 6G technologies, the utilization of higher frequencies such as mmWaves (millimeter waves), sub-THz, and THz (terahertz) has emerged as a significant advancement. These higher frequency bands offer enhanced communication bandwidths and sensing capabilities, paving the way for novel applications and techniques. Additionally, the development of Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) technologies, which encompass the integration of communication and sensing functionalities, leads to synergistic benefits and improved system performance. JCAS has drawn a lot of attention from the academy due to its potential for 6G systems, as it makes it possible to reduce equipment costs, size, and power consumption, while simultaneously improving spectral efficiency, hardware resource utilization, and information processing efficiency.

In addition, the integration of higher frequencies such as mmWaves, sub-THz, and THz in 6G technologies presents numerous advantages. Firstly, these frequency bands offer a considerably larger bandwidth, enabling higher data rates and increased capacity for communication systems. Secondly, the shorter wavelength associated with higher frequencies facilitates the deployment of more compact antennas, thereby enabling the realization of small form-factor devices and networks. Additionally, higher frequencies provide improved spatial resolution for sensing applications, allowing for enhanced object detection, tracking, and localization.

Despite the above advantages, the development of JCAS systems also brings up a few challenges such as

1. **Suitable waveform:** designing a waveform that is capable of efficiently carrying information while using the available bandwidths in the sub-THz/THz bands while also providing good sensing performance (which implies good time-frequency correlation properties, to achieve accurate positioning) is a significant challenge. In the academia, various approaches are being studied, including single-carrier modulations, multicarrier modulations such as Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM), and Single-Carrier Frequency Division Multiplexing (SC-FDM) modulations, among others. Each waveform has its advantages and disadvantages in terms of spectral efficiency, resilience to frequency-selective fading, complexity, and coexistence with sensing functionality.
2. **Balance between the sensing capabilities and the information capacity of the communication system:** Sensing requires high spatial and time resolution to accurately detect and analyze the environment, while communication demands high data rates and reliable connectivity. There is an inherent tradeoff between these two objectives¹. Optimizing the waveform design to achieve an acceptable compromise

¹ J. A. Zhang *et al.*, "An Overview of Signal Processing Techniques for Joint Communication and Radar Sensing," in *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1295-1315, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JSTSP.2021.3113120.

between sensing resolution and communication capacity is a major challenge in the design process.

3. **Low-cost platforms:** The unavailability of low-cost, commercial end-to-end platforms is a bottleneck for sub-THz/THz frequency bands due to the lack of affordable, off-the-shelf platforms specifically designed for experimentation in sub-THz/THz frequency bands. Most existing platforms are based on specialized instrumentation or high-end processing systems, which can be prohibitively expensive. This limitation makes it challenging for researchers and developers to conduct experiments and prototype new technologies without significant financial resources.
4. **Limited availability of components:** Sub-THz/THz links require specific components such as amplifiers and up/downconverters tailored for these frequency ranges. However, finding commercially available models and manufacturers for these components can be difficult. The limited supply chain and availability of sub-THz/THz components pose challenges in sourcing the necessary hardware for building communication systems operating in these frequency bands.
5. **Baseband processing requirements:** Sub-THz/THz communications often involve high data rates due to the large available bandwidth. Meeting the requirements for baseband processing, which involves tasks such as modulation, demodulation, error correction, and signal processing, becomes challenging. Handling such high bit rates necessitates specialized hardware architectures and efficient algorithms to ensure real-time processing and maintain system performance.

Overcoming these limitations will require the design and implementation of cost-effective, customizable platforms, as well as efforts to expand the availability of components suitable for sub-THz/THz links. In addition, advancements in baseband processing technologies will be necessary to handle the high data rates associated with these frequency bands. Addressing these hardware challenges will be crucial for the successful development and deployment of sub-THz/THz integrated sensing and communications in 6G networks.

JCAS technologies are poised to undergo three distinct stages^{2 3}, namely coexistence, mutual assistance, and mutual benefit:

1. **Coexistence:** In this initial stage, communication and sensing functions operate independently within the same system. Communication and sensing systems can coexist side by side, utilizing separate equipment and spectrum resources.
2. **Mutual Assistance:** The second stage involves communication and sensing systems supporting each other by sharing certain resources, such as antennas or spectrum. This collaboration between communication and sensing components leads to improved performance and resource efficiency.

² J. A. Zhang et al., "Enabling Joint Communication and Radar Sensing in Mobile Networks - A Survey," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 306–345, 2022, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2021.3122519.

³ J. A. Zhang et al., "An Overview of Signal Processing Techniques for Joint Communication and Radar Sensing," in *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1295-1315, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JSTSP.2021.3113120.

3. **Mutual Benefit:** The final stage of JCAS evolution entails a fully integrated system where communication and sensing functions synergistically enhance each other, resulting in mutual benefits. At this stage, the same set of equipment and/or spectrum can be leveraged to simultaneously accomplish communication and sensing tasks. This integration leads to reduced equipment costs, smaller device footprints, lower power consumption, enhanced spectral efficiency, improved hardware resource utilization, and increased information processing efficiency.

5 Hardware platform

This section includes two subsections, 1) high level design and 2) state of the art.

5.1 High level design

The proposed scheme for the sub-THz link is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 5.1.1. Sub-THz link

As it can be seen in Figure 5.1.1., the sub-THz link comprises the following elements:

- **Transmitter:** There is a baseband generator that synthesizes four signals with a bandwidth of 400 MHz, each with a different intermediate frequency (IF). Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) platforms based on software-defined radio (SDR), such as USRPs or Xilinx RFSocCs, may be employed for this purpose. Subsequently, the four signals are combined into one and modulated to sub-THz frequencies using a VDI upconverter, and the resulting signal is radiated using a horn antenna.
- **Receiver:** A similar processing chain is employed: the radio-frequency signal is received by a horn antenna and then down converted to IF using a VDI downconverter. Then, a splitter decomposes the signal into its four fundamental carriers, and finally, each carrier is demodulated separately in the baseband processing stage.

The data input and output interfaces for the transmitter and receiver, respectively, will accept and deliver Ethernet traffic. Note as well that, in the current design, the sub-THz link is unidirectional, as its main goal is to serve as a proof of concept for JCAS communications. If the use case where this link is to be integrated requires bidirectional communications, the forward, sub-THz link could be complemented with a return link that employs a secondary off-band radio channel, for example.

The below steps summarize the development of the link is that an incremental approach:

- 1) A sub-THz link will be implemented using waveguides as the channel between the TX and RX, along with a shared local oscillator. This setup will be used to verify the uplink and downlink stages to sub-THz without generating extreme frequency offsets or phase noise issues.
- 2) A single oscillator will be added for both the transmitter and receiver. This oscillator will be obtained from an RF sinusoidal generator to avoid problems related to phase noise in commercial equipment.
- 3) Antennas are added to the link to provide a wireless channel, and tests can be conducted with independent local oscillators based on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components.

This approach leverages COTS baseband processing platforms supported by large developer communities, aiming to achieve a flexible and cost-effective link that maximizes the capacity to deploy generic waveforms with minimal development time.

The specific choice of the baseband processing platform will depend on the waveform design and will be determined in the future. The goal is to select a platform that best suits the requirements and characteristics of the chosen waveform. This allows for adaptability and the ability to leverage existing resources and expertise within the development community.

By adopting this approach, the development process can be streamlined, costs can be minimized, and the potential for innovation and customization can be maximized. It provides the flexibility to explore various waveform designs and adapt them to different applications or scenarios as needed in the future.

5.2 State of the art

This section presents a brief overview of the state of the art related to hardware platforms for THz/sub-THz communications, sensing and experimentation in general.

5.2.1 Existing experimental platforms for THz/Sub-THz communications

Currently there exist several commercial platforms that offer turnkey solutions to build a THz/sub-THz link. Those platforms are usually based on laboratory instrumentation and/or closed hardware components such as

- **National Instruments Sub-THz and mmWave Transceiver System^{4 5 6}**: It is built on the modular hardware systems developed by this company. The Sub-THz and mmWave Transceiver System implements a digital communications link that can work

⁴ <https://www.ni.com/es/solutions/electronics/5g-6g-wireless-research-prototyping/research-prototype-5g-mmwave-systems.html>

⁵ <https://www.ni.com/es-es/shop/wireless-design-test/what-is-mmwave-transceiver-system.html>

⁶ <https://www.everythingrf.com/News/details/9000-NI-Launches-Sub-THz-Testbed-for-6G-Research>

on either the 28 or 39 GHz frequency bands. In addition, if Virginia Diodes (VDI) extension modules⁷ are used, then frequencies up to 170 GHz are reachable for the link. This system has a real-time bandwidth of 2 GHz throughout the system, enabling efficient data transmission and reception. The LabView⁸ graphical programming environment is used to operate and monitor the link, as well as a development framework for experimenting with new functional blocks and algorithms. Regarding the modulations supported by this platform, the Sub-THz and mmWave Transceiver System offers two physical layer configurations to suit different needs. One is a single-carrier transmission scheme, while the other uses a multicarrier modulation. These options allow users to choose the configuration that best suits their requirements and to test the performance of different waveforms under different scenarios. Also, the basic configuration of this platform allows for the implementation of a SISO (Single Input Single Output) link, but this configuration can be extended to support MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) by adding additional transmitter/receiver (TX/RX) chains.

- **Keysight commercial platform⁹ for 6G sub-THz/THz:** This platform comprises mainly high-end laboratory equipment such as signal generators, oscilloscopes, and spectrum analyzers. A major component used by the Keysight platform is the M8195A¹⁰ multi-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), which has a signal generation capability of up to 65 GSa/s. This AWG enables the generation of wideband signals combined with a high-speed oscilloscope of the Infiniium family¹¹ with a sampling rate of up to 33 GHz, which acts as a general-purpose receiver along with the 89600 Vector Signal Analysis (VSA) software, offered by the same manufacturer¹². Keysight's platform also benefits from the use of VDI extension modules, allowing the extension of the frequency range to 220 GHz. This high-frequency capability provides opportunities for testing and analysis in millimeter and sub-terahertz bands. It is worth mentioning that one of the available demonstrations of the Keysight solution showcases the use of a 10 GHz bandwidth QAM signal operating at 144 GHz.

The attractiveness of these platforms mainly lies in the fact that they provide high-performance, high-bandwidth hardware with minimal development required from the user, as they are offered as turnkey solutions. However, the downside of these platforms is their exceedingly high cost, and the limited portability of the designs developed on top of them, for instance toward lower-cost platforms comprising blocks that are closer to what an actual consumer implementation

⁷ VDI extension modules: <https://www.vadiodes.com/en/products/vector-network-analyzer-extension-modules>

⁸ LabView: <https://www.ni.com/en-us/shop/labview.html>

⁹ 6G Sub-Terahertz R&D Testbed: <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/products/modular/reference-solutions/6g-sub-terahertz-r-d-testbed.html>

¹⁰ M8195A 65 GSa/s Arbitrary Waveform Generator: <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/product/M8195A/65-gsa-s-arbitrary-waveform-generator.html>

¹¹ Keysight Infiniium family <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/products/oscilloscopes/infiniium-real-time-oscilloscopes/infiniium-uxr-series-oscilloscopes.html>

¹² 89600 VSA software (now called PathWave VSA)

<https://www.keysight.com/us/en/products/software/pathwave-test-software/89600-vsa-software.html>

would be. Manufacturers such as Keysight and National Instruments also provide exemplary reference designs, but they are not publicly available and hence there is no known supporting user communities supporting new developments, as it happens, for instance, with well-known Software Defined Radios (SDRs) such as Ettus Research USRPs^{13 14}.

5.2.2 Customizable platforms

In contrast to the turnkey solutions previously discussed, various custom-built platforms have also been developed in the field of THz research, combining laboratory equipment with COTS (Commercial Off-The-Shelf) elements and even SDRs. These platforms also provide options for conducting experiments and testing in the field of ultra-wideband wireless communications. It is important to note that most of those platforms are based on expensive instrumentation and equipment. In some cases, they do not support sensing applications or JCAS, and the baseband processing stage is not always based on commercially available equipment, which may limit their adaptability to other scenarios and their flexibility.

Notable examples include the Testbed **6G Flagship** at the University of Oulu, the **ThoR Project**, and the **TERRANOVA** project led by Fraunhofer and Intracom Telecom.

- a) **6G Flagship Testbed**¹⁵: it is developed at the University of Oulu. It combines sub-THz/THz extension modules from VDI with high-end instrumentation in a similar way to the Keysight testbed. They have published different works focusing mainly on sensing applications up to 330 GHz, and characterization of custom blocks for THz applications¹⁶.
- b) **ThoR Project**¹⁷: it is a custom-built platform designed for point-to-point links at 300 GHz. The platform utilizes equipment from Wavetech. However, this platform does not include JCAS capabilities.
- c) **TERRANOVA project**^{18 19}: The developers claim that its advanced architecture and comprehensive set of development tools provide a solid foundation for experimentation and the development of wireless technologies in the THz range. However, not many technical details are publicly available. The platform does not appear to offer support for JCAS either.

¹³ Ettus: <https://www.ettus.com/>

¹⁴ GNU Radio mailing list: <https://wiki.gnuradio.org/index.php/MailingLists>

¹⁵ 6G FLAGSHIP: <https://www.6gflagship.com/news/thz-sensing-in-focus-novel-radio-lenses/>

¹⁶ 6G FLAGSHIP Measurement and Proof of Concept Capabilities Up to 300 GHz: <https://www.6gflagship.com/news/measurement-and-proof-of-concept-capabilities-up-to-330-ghz/>

¹⁷ ThoR Project: <https://thorproject.eu>

¹⁸ SEN, Priyangshu, et al. The TeraNova platform: An integrated testbed for ultra-broadband wireless communications at true Terahertz frequencies. *Computer Networks*, 2020, vol. 179, p. 107370.

¹⁹ Terranova EU Research Project <https://www.hhi.fraunhofer.de/en/news/nachrichten/2020/eu-research-project-terranova-fraunhofer-hhi-shows-first-ever-100-gb-s-thz-free-space-transmission-with-polarization-multiplex-over-500-meters-distance.html>

Next, we will focus on alternatives based on SDRs, particularly the RFSoc family of System-on-Chips (SoCs) offered by Xilinx²⁰. These SoCs integrate very high-speed analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog converters along with an ARM processor and a large FPGA, all in the same package. Another interesting type of SDR platform is the Ettus Research USRPs. The latest families of USRPs, namely the USRP X410, leverage a RFSoc at its core to provide up to four 400-MHz channels. The technical details and possibilities of these platforms are reviewed further below in this document. Sub-THz/THz platforms based on these kinds of SDRs have emerged as a prominent option in the development of ultra-wideband wireless communications, mainly due to their flexibility and lower cost.

These solutions, developed by Northeastern University in Boston and Florida International University in Miami, aim to achieve high-speed data transmission in the terahertz spectrum. It is worth noting that these alternatives exclusively concentrate on the communications aspect and do not encompass sensing applications.

Covering front-end frequencies from 95-120 GHz, 120-140 GHz, 200 -240 GHz, and 1-1.05 THz, this approach offers a wide range of terahertz bands. It supports bandwidths ranging from 2 GHz to 32 GHz, providing ample capacity for data-intensive applications.

At the core of this approach lies the Xilinx RFSoc (Radio Frequency System on Chip), incorporating 8 high-speed digital-to-analog converters (DACs) and 8 analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) operating at 4.096 GSPS (Giga-Samples Per Second). These capabilities ensure efficient data conversion and processing within the terahertz range. Radiofrequency (RF) front ends are designed by VDI. The system utilizes OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing) modulation based on the IEEE 802.11a standard, employing 64 carriers. The digital cores are specifically designed to support BPSK, QPSK, 16-QAM, and 64-QAM modulations.

A notable demonstration²¹ of this approach involves a system operating at 130 GHz, with two active channels providing a 2.048 GHz bandwidth each and utilizing QPSK modulation. This showcases the system's capabilities in handling high-frequency data transmission.

The implementation of this approach in a prototype²² utilizes the ZCU111 development board. It generates two baseband channels from the RFSoc and utilizes IQ mixers with local oscillators at frequencies of 3 GHz and 5.5 GHz. A 2-way combiner is used to aggregate two channels with 2 GHz bandwidth, resulting in a 4 GHz intermediate frequency (IF) signal.

The front-end hardware consists of two frequency multipliers, a mixer with a 7dB double sideband conversion loss, an RF power amplifier with 20 dB gain, a low-noise down-converter

²⁰ Zynq UltraScale+ RFSoc: <https://www.xilinx.com/products/silicon-devices/soc/rfsoc.html>

²¹ ABDELLATIF, Hussam, et al. A Real-Time Ultra-broadband Software-Defined Radio Platform for Terahertz Communications. En *IEEE INFOCOM 2022-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*. IEEE, 2022. p. 1-2.

²² SEN, Priyanshu, et al. Experimental wireless testbed for ultrabroadband terahertz networks. En *Proceedings of the 14th International Workshop on Wireless Network Testbeds, Experimental evaluation & Characterization*. 2020. p. 48-55.

mixer, and a low-noise amplifier (LNA) with 12 dB gain. This carefully designed setup ensures optimal signal processing and amplification for efficient terahertz communications.

5.2.3 Sub-THz/THz COTS equipment

To develop commercial RF equipment, which can cover sub-THz frequencies, several solutions have been developed that extend the capabilities of measurement equipment such as vector network analyzers (VNAs) or spectrum analyzers. This equipment enables efficient broadband frequency conversions and opens new opportunities for the development of 6G applications.

One of the leading manufacturers in this field is Rohde & Schwarz, which offers a number of front-ends²³ specifically designed to extend the frequency of its own measurement equipment into the sub-terahertz range. Other notable products are offered by Radiometer Physics, an affiliate company of Rohde & Schwarz, which offers specialized equipment capable of performing signal frequency downconversion²⁴ as well as upconversion²⁵.

On the other hand, VDI is renowned for its range of equipment²⁶ capable of performing up/downconversion processes covering a wide range of frequencies, from 90 GHz to 1.1 THz. They are more generic than Rohde & Schwarz and therefore allow more versatility when using other measurement equipment.

In addition to the above-mentioned manufacturers, there are other frequency mixing devices on the market that also allow upconversion and downconversion processes. However, these devices require local oscillators of higher frequencies for their operation. An example of this are the mixers of the brand Millimeter Wave Products Inc (Mi-Wave)²⁷.

It is worth mentioning that in the context of sub-THz frequencies, it is common to use waveguide-based interfaces for equipment connectors. However, it is important to note that all commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) equipment using waveguides is highly dependent on the operating frequency. This is partly due to the fact that there are mechanical standards that limit the operating frequencies of the equipment, which is a drawback when covering large bandwidths.

²³ Frequency range extender front ends: https://www.rohde-schwarz.com/es/productos/test-y-medida/front-ends-y-convertidores_333592.html

²⁴ Spectrum analyser extenders for downconversion: <https://www.radiometer-physics.de/products/mmwave-and-terahertz-products/spectrum-analyzer-extendere/fs-z-mixers/>

²⁵ Signal Generator Extenders for upconversion: <https://www.radiometer-physics.de/products/mmwave-and-terahertz-products/signal-generator-extendere/ztx-series-for-signal-generators/>

²⁶ Spectrum Analyzer Extension (SAX) modules: <https://www.vadiodes.com/en/products/spectrum-analyzer>

²⁷ Mi-wave's RF Upconverters and downconverters for W-band: <https://www.miww.com/95-ghz-to-100-ghz-w-band-up-downconverter/>

To establish a link of a few meters, the use of amplifiers is required. Although they are relatively rare at these frequencies, there are manufacturers such as Eravant²⁸, Erzia²⁹ or Pasternack³⁰ who offer amplifiers suitable for covering this frequency range. Some manufacturers already mentioned such as VDI³¹ or Radiometer Physics³² also offer amplifiers for the sub-THz frequencies.

Due to the use of the frequency converters mentioned above, it is necessary to use bandpass filters to remove unwanted image frequencies and replicas. Manufacturers such as Eravant³³ have models with relatively narrow bandwidths (a few GHz) allowing good frequency filtering. Other manufacturers such as VDI³⁴ offer less selective filters, making them less ideal for signal filtering.

Typical antennas in this frequency range are horn antennas, and they have the particularity of being quite directive, for example, the antennas provided by VDI³⁵ have a 3 dB beamwidth of between 13 and 10°. Other manufacturers offering this type of antenna are Eravant³⁶ or RF-Lambda³⁷.

Besides, isolators are recommended to prevent damage to upconverters due to unwanted reflections. Although the variety of models is limited, manufacturers such as Eravant³⁸ and Micro Harmonics³⁹ offer suitable isolators to cover the sub-THz frequencies in this project.

5.2.4 SDR baseband processing platforms

There are two main types of SDRs as follows.

5.2.4.1 Ettus Research USRP X410

The USRP X410 is an SDR baseband processing platform manufactured by Ettus Research. It is designed for software-defined radio applications and provides a wide frequency range and real-time processing capability. It supports frequencies from 1 MHz up to 7.2 GHz, with

²⁸ Eravant waveguide amplifiers: <https://www.eravant.com/products/amplifiers/power-amplifiers>

²⁹ Erzia waveguide amplifiers: <https://www.erzia.com/products/lna>

³⁰ Pasternack waveguide amplifiers:

https://www.pasternack.com/nsearch.aspx?Category=Waveguide+Power+Amplifiers&sort=y&initial_sort=Sortsku:ASC&res_per_page=48&view_type=grid

³¹ VDI waveguide amplifiers: <https://www.vadiodes.com/en/products/amplifier>

³² Radiometer Physics waveguide amplifiers <https://www.radiometer-physics.de/products/mmwave-and-terahertz-products/amplifiers/low-noise-amplifiers/>

³³ Eravant waveguide filters: <https://www.eravant.com/products/filters/waveguide-filters>

³⁴ VDI waveguide filters: <https://www.vadiodes.com/en/products/amplifiers-filters>

³⁵ VDI horn antennas: https://www.vadiodes.com/images/AppNotes/VDI_Feedhorn_Summary_2020.05.04.pdf

³⁶ Eravant horn antennas: <https://www.eravant.com/products/antennas/horn-antennas>

³⁷ RF-Lambda antennas: https://www.rflambda.com/search_wgantenna.jsp

³⁸ Eravant isolators: <https://www.eravant.com/products/faraday-isolators>

³⁹ Micro Harmonics isolators and Faraday rotators: <https://www.microharmonics.com/documents/faraday-rotation-isolators/>

tunability up to 8 GHz. The device offers a high sampling rate and a wide bandwidth range, making it suitable for applications that require high signal processing capability.

The USRP X410 is compatible with various frameworks and development tools, making it easy to integrate into software-defined radio projects. Each USRP X410 comes with two ZBX boards, providing a total of 4 channels of analog bandwidth, with each channel capable of up to 400 MHz. It is important to note that the analog bandwidth depends on both the software and the hardware used, as well as the FPGA image employed.

FPGA images are available with a bandwidth of 200 MHz (tested and supported) and 400 MHz (experimental). In terms of interfaces, the USRP X410 features 2xQSFP28 ports for data download and control, supporting 100 GbE, and 1xPCIe Gen3 x8. Additionally, it offers interfaces for command, control and debugging, including USB-C, USB-c JTAG, Ethernet 10/100/1000 and 2xHDMI.

Regarding RF capabilities, the USRP X410 has 4 TX channels and 4 RX channels. To utilize it optimally, a recommended host PC should have a minimum of 15 CPU cores, 32 GB of RAM and Ubuntu 20.04 as the operating system.

5.2.4.2 Xilinx RFSocS

The Xilinx RFSoc is a family of System-on-Chip devices aimed at SDR applications. It combines an ARM processor with a traditional FPGA, and several GSPS-class Analog-to-Digital and Digital-to-Analog converters on a single chip. More specifically, among these converters are up to 8 12-bit ADCs with a maximum rate of 4.096 GSPS, as well as 8 14-bit DACs with a maximum rate of 6.554 GSPS. These converters allow synthesizing and sampling signals with bandwidths of up to several GHz. Optionally, some RFSoc models also feature Soft-Decision Forward Error Correction (SD-FEC) blocks that implement LPDC (Low-Density Parity Check) and Turbo encoding and decoding.

Overall, RFSoc devices constitute a powerful solution for SDR applications, combining FPGA processing capabilities with high-speed data conversion for broadband signal synthesis and sampling.

Currently there are three generations of RFSocS, each with increasing capabilities:

- Gen1: Integrates up to sixteen 12-bit, 4-GSPS ADCs, up to sixteen 14-bit, 6.5-GSPS DACs, and up to eight SD-FECs.
- Gen2: Integrates ADCs with wider RF input bandwidth.
- Gen3: Integrates 14-bit, 5-GSPS ADCs and 10-GSPS DACs, and introduces a subfamily called Gen 3 DFE (Digital Front-End) that integrates the DFE hard IP block, containing specific functional blocks for 5G PHY-layer functions.

Also, RFSoc devices are available in the form of development boards, many of them offered by Xilinx along with software frameworks and configuration presets that speed up developments. Some examples include the ZCU111, ZCU218, ZCU208, ZCU216, and

ZCU670⁴⁰. Lower-capacity development kits aiming at academic training and universities are also available⁴¹. It is worth noting that these development boards are also interface-rich, often featuring USB, Gigabit Ethernet, QSFP+, SATA and other common interfaces.

6 Communications system

This section includes the following contents:

- The first subsection introduces a summary of the state of the art in regard to sub-THz communication systems, highlighting some of the waveforms that are currently being proposed and experimented with on those frequencies.
- The second subsection provides a high-level design of the proposed communication system.

6.1 State of the art

Sub-terahertz (sub-THz) communications systems are an emerging area of research and development. Sub-THz refers to frequencies in the range of 100 GHz to 1 THz, which lies between the microwave and infrared frequency bands. These frequencies offer several potential advantages for wireless communications, including high data rates, large bandwidths, and potential for small form factor devices. Communications systems working at this band can achieve point-to-point connectivity with data rates of 100 Gb/s and higher at distances ranging from tens of centimeters up to a few hundred meters, which promises to be an essential ingredient of future ultra-broadband wireless technologies^{42 43}.

The peculiarities of the THz-band channel (frequency/distance-dependency and sparsity) impose challenging constraints on the physical layer of future wireless standards. Sub-THz signals suffer from severe path loss, limiting the transmission distances to a few meters⁴⁴. However, long distance sub-THz communications (over hundreds of meters) are still feasible with high-gain antenna arrays⁴⁵. The frequency selective molecular absorption further results in distance-dependent spectrum fragmentation and shrinking (variable bandwidth transmission windows)⁴⁶. Furthermore, since the line-of-sight (LoS) path dominates THz-band signal propagation, THz channels tend to be flat-fading. However, a few multi-path components might

⁴⁰ Zynq UltraScale+ RFSoc Boards, Kits, and Modules: <https://www.xilinx.com/products/boards-and-kits/device-family/nav-zynq-ultrascale-plus-rfsoc.html>

⁴¹ Academic FPGA and SOC Development Boards: <https://www.xilinx.com/support/university/xup-boards.html>

⁴² I. F. Akyildiz, J. M. Jornet, and C. Han, "Terahertz band: Next frontier for wireless communications," *Physical Commun.*, vol. 12, pp. 16–32, Sep. 2014.

⁴³ H. Elayan, O. Amin, B. Shihada, R. M. Shubair, and M.-S. Alouini, "Terahertz band: The last piece of RF spectrum puzzle for communication

⁴⁴ J. M. Jornet and I. F. Akyildiz, "Channel modeling and capacity analysis for electromagnetic wireless nanonetworks in the terahertz band," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 3211–3221, 2011

⁴⁵ G. Gougeon, Y. Corre, M. Z. Aslam, S. Bicaïs, and J.-B. Doré, "Assessment of sub-thz mesh backhaul capabilities from realistic modeling at the phy layer," in *Proc. IEEE Euro. Conf. on Ant. and Prop. (EuCAP)*, 2020, pp. 1–5.

⁴⁶ I. F. Akyildiz, C. Han, and S. Nie, "Combating the distance problem in the millimeter wave and terahertz frequency bands," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 102–108, 2018

persist, especially in indoor scenarios, resulting in frequency-selective channels with coherence bandwidths of hundreds of megahertz (MHz) over medium communication distances⁴⁷. Therefore, THz multicarrier (MC) schemes retain scenario-specific benefits. Designing efficient THz-specific waveforms is crucial for unleashing the THz-band's true capabilities.

6.2 Waveform design considerations

The prospects of utilizing either single-carrier (SC) or multi-carrier (MC) waveforms in sub-THz band communication systems remain a matter of carefully weighing the pros and cons. On the one hand, the limited multi-path components at high frequencies result in frequency-flat channels that favor low-complexity wideband SC systems. On the other hand, frequency-dependent molecular absorption and transceiver characteristics and the existence of multi-path components in indoor sub-THz systems can still result in frequency-selective channels, favoring off-the-shelf MC schemes such as OFDM. Variations of SC/MC designs result in different THz spectrum utilization, but spectral efficiency is not the primary concern with substantial available bandwidths; baseband complexity, power efficiency, and hardware impairment constraints are predominant.

The different waveform designs that have been found for the sub-THz band communication systems in the most recent publications can be grouped into three main categories, whose main characteristics are described below.

6.2.1 Typical multi-carrier waveform

Among these waveforms we can find OFDM and DFT-s-OFDM). Their main characteristics are:

- High flexibility and commonly used in modern wireless communication systems.
- In high-mobility scenarios (e.g., automotive, drones), inter-carrier interference (ICI) is a significant challenge for OFDM radar, degrading performance.
- High peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR), which affects power amplifier (PA) efficiency and requires operation with back-off to avoid distortion.
- At sub-THz frequency range, the channel coherence time decreases. This means that the channel state changes more rapidly, requiring more frequent estimation to accurately track channel variations.

6.2.2 Typical single-carrier waveform

Their main characteristics are:

⁴⁷ C. Han, A. O. Bicen, and I. F. Akyildiz, "Multi-ray channel modeling and wideband characterization for wireless communications in the terahertz band," IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun., vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 2402–2412, 2014

- Single-carrier waveforms (e.g., IEEE 802.11ad⁴⁸) are more attractive from a hardware perspective but should be carefully designed to avoid high side-lobe levels.
- Low PAPR improves efficiency of power amplifier (PA) devices operating at sub-THz range.
- The pulse shaping filter must be correctly designed to shape the transmitted waveform to reduce bandwidth and control interference.

6.2.3 Novel experimental waveforms

There exists an increasing interest in designing new waveforms for 6G system with different purposes and optimization criteria. Among the recent literature we can find SC-FDE (Single Carrier with Frequency Domain Equalization)⁴⁹ or DE-MS-QP (Data-Embedded Multi-Subband Quasi-Perfect)⁵⁰. They offer specific advantages such as reducing PAPR and phase noise. However, there exists just one or a few studies on them, and their results were obtained by making certain assumptions (e.g., ignoring IQ imbalance, nonlinearities, or channel response). The results achieved are based on simulations and they are yet to be tested in real environments, i.e., too far away from being practical and functional waveforms.

6.2.4 Waveform design conclusion

Overall, multi-carrier waveforms offer high flexibility, but face challenges related to inter-carrier interference and high PAPR. Single-carrier waveforms, specifically SC-FDE, provide improvements in PAPR reduction, phase noise estimation, and quantization, with a focus on hardware implementation. Proper design of pulse shaping filters is important for both waveform types. Despite the numerous options that can be found in current research, a significant portion of publications tends to focus on waveforms based on OFDM (or any of its variations), mainly due to its suitability for current 5G systems and future 6G systems. In other words, the 5G framework offers an ideal foundation from which waveform designs can be reused and adapted to the project needs or can serve as inspiration to design new brand customized proprietary waveforms that work in the sub-THz band. Furthermore, 5G is backed by solid technical specifications on advanced topics such as MIMO, beamforming and multiuser systems that can prove to be useful for a tailored waveform design.

There are also initial standardization efforts for sub-THz band communications toward 6G⁵¹. Harnessing the frequencies above 100 GHz is planned for 6G and beyond solutions as a key enabler for new applications demanding ultra-high user data rates exceeding tens of gigabits per second and providing continuous bands of hundreds, or even thousands, of gigahertz. The

⁴⁸ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/802.11ad/4527/>

⁴⁹ L. H. Nguyen, V. Braun, H. Halbauer and T. Wild, "Waveform Comparison under Hardware Limitations for 6G Sub-THz Communications," *2022 IEEE 19th Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference*

⁵⁰ T. Mao, J. Chen, Q. Wang, C. Han, "Waveform Design for Joint Sensing and Communications in Millimeter-Wave and Low Terahertz Bands," in *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 70, no. 10, Oct. 2022

⁵¹ V. Petrov, T. Kurner and I. Hosako, "IEEE 802.15.3d: First Standardization Efforts for Sub-Terahertz Band Communications toward 6G," in *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 28-33

major players from academia, industry, standardization, and regulatory bodies have been actively exploring the feasibility of such communications over the last decades. A significant milestone in this direction was achieved with the ratification of the IEEE 802.15.3d⁵² amendment to 802.15.3, which seeks to establish standardized consumer wireless communications in the sub-terahertz frequency band. This amendment defines a wireless physical layer (PHY) that operates at a speed of 100 Gb/s, with the potential to fall back to lower rates. The primary objective is to demonstrate the practicality of sub-terahertz communications and establish a standard for low-complexity, high-rate connectivity. However, it should be noted that the considered deployments are currently limited to point-to-point links between stationary or quasi-static devices during data exchange⁵³.

⁵² <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/802.15.3d/6648/>

⁵³ T. Kürner et al., “Applications Requirement Document (ARD),” IEEE 802.15-14-0304-16-003d, May 2015

6.3 Communication system high level design

Based on the analysis of the state of the art reviewed in the previous section and noting the research trends in sub-THz communication systems, this project proposes the design of a **multicarrier waveform** based on the transmission method known as **OFDM**, where a single information stream is split among several closely spaced narrowband subchannel frequencies instead of a single wideband channel frequency.

OFDM offers several advantages over traditional single-carrier modulation schemes, such as better spectral efficiency, resistance to frequency-selective fading, mitigation of interference, adaptive bit and power allocation, and easier equalization, to name a few. On the other hand, this type of waveform does require to be carefully designed in order to avoid potential problems like having a high Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR), intercarrier interference or synchronization issues; specially in a fast-changing channel mainly due to operating at such high frequencies.

Apart from the standard OFDM, also known as CP-OFDM (Cyclic Prefix OFDM), there are other numerous variants (ZP-OFDM, C-OFDM, F-OFDM, DFT-s-OFDM, ...) ⁵⁴ that have ever been proposed, studied, experimented with, and even commercially used in systems such as 5G or WLAN. Each one of these waveforms comes with its own advantages and disadvantages. Thus, one should be carefully picked from among all of them choosing the one which better adapts to the project needs and the defined use cases. This selection requires a more in-depth analysis and testing outside the scope of this initial high-level design. Eventually, if neither of them seems to be suitable, there is also the possibility to design a custom waveform inspired on one of those variants, but making the necessary changes so that the project requirements are met.

In the previous subsection, it was also mentioned that most of the existing studies and experimental testbeds of communications on the sub-THz band were based on 5G architecture, taking advantage of being a mature technology with solid specifications. 5G not only offers robust and efficient communication methods but also an infrastructure that can support various advanced techniques like MIMO or beamforming, which can be useful and relevant in future sub-THz communications. Therefore, the **waveform design** for this project is proposed to be **primarily based on or inspired by 5G / 6G technology whenever feasible** and in accordance with the project needs.

The designing of a customized waveform is mostly impacting the physical layer, but also the MAC (Medium Access Control) layer is of great importance. 5G protocol stack already provides some interesting blocks in both layers that can be reusable and adaptable for the sub-THz communication system. Some of these reusable items can be, for example: data encoders and decoders, modulation, constellations, reference signals, pilots, time, and synchronization algorithms, and so on.

Additionally, much effort is currently being devoted to open-source libraries that implement the various network elements of a 5G architecture, such as OpenAirInterface⁵⁵ or srsRAN⁵⁶. Any of these libraries could serve as an initial basis for the development of the sub-THz waveform. As an example, OAI gNB already supports bandwidths up to 100 MHz on FR1 and FR2 bands, and they have extensive improvements already planned in their roadmap for the upcoming years⁵⁷.

The following figure shows a basic diagram of a 5G OFDM modulation system.

Figure 6.3.1. Basic OFDM system: transmitter and receiver

Information bits are first error protected, then OFDM modulated and then transmitted. In some designs the LDPC encoder is coupled together with a BCH outer code scheme to ensure superior performance in an environment with high noise levels and interference. The inner LDPC code supports the generation of long codes that have a powerful and robust error correction capability, while the outer BCH codes reduce the error floor of the LDPC code. Whether to include a BCH encoder or not will be evaluated during the transceiver implementation process, as well as deciding which code rates should be supported.

⁵⁴ B. Amine, K. Zoukalne, M. Saleh, "A Comprehensive Survey of Candidate Waveforms for 5G, beyond 5G and 6G Wireless Communication Systems", *Open Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2023

⁵⁵ <https://openairinterface.org/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.srslte.com/>

⁵⁷ <https://openairinterface.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/2022-07-12-EURECOM-RAN-SLIDES.pdf>

There is also an important design decision regarding how the communication system will be able to achieve large bandwidths. Due to hardware limitations, as discussed in the previous section, the maximum bandwidth supported per channel is 400 MHz, at least in the COTS platforms currently being considered. The proposed solution to achieve larger bandwidths is to have the baseband generator synthesize four signals with a bandwidth of 400 MHz, each with a different intermediate frequency (IF), and then combine them all together to form a single output signal. This process is illustrated in the following diagram (Fig. 6.3.2) as an example for the transmitter.

Figure 6.3.2. Flow combination to form the 1.6 GHz bandwidth.

The incoming streaming data to be split among the different channels will be the responsibility of the MAC layer, or even a higher entity if required. Then, several modulators (physical layer) can work in parallel to generate each baseband signal. In the initial design, a simple split is proposed that evenly distributes the data among the available resources, and there will be no interdependencies among the different channels. The receiver should be able to filter each channel individually and process them independently to eventually reconstruct the original data stream. It is important not to confuse this with 5G concepts like channel bonding or carrier aggregation since these techniques apply different advanced processing algorithms and somehow make channels dependent on each other.

Following the same methodology for hardware design in the previous section, the development of the communication system will follow an incremental approach as well:

- Start by having a communication system using only one channel of 100 MHz (as OpenAirInterface does) working at sub-THz frequencies in a simulated environment. This system will be unidirectional and will support only one user.
- Integrate the communications system into the hardware platform to test its performance.
- Proceed to extend its functionality so that more than one channel can be used simultaneously, up to four channels of 100 MHz each.
- Increase the bandwidth of the channels from 100 MHz to 400 MHz.
- Integration with the sensing system and extensive testing.
- Integration and validation with i2CAT.

Note that not all these steps need to be followed chronologically and their order can be altered or even done in parallel during the development phase.

7 Sensing system

This section covers all aspects related to the sensing system. Initially, we review the state of the art, where we will define what sensing is, the different types of radar, their classification, representation, and basic parameters, as well as the different types of integration with communications systems. Then, the best option for the use case presented in this document is detailed and justified. Finally, the high-level design for the sensing part is described.

7.1 State of the art

In the rapidly evolving landscape of technological advances, radar and sensor systems have emerged as critical tools in various domains. These systems facilitate the collection of valuable information about our surroundings, object detection, distance measurement and comprehensive environmental insight. At the heart of these systems is the concept of sensing, which encompasses a wide range of applications from radar and user equipment positioning to imaging and spectroscopy. Understanding the fundamental principles and diverse applications of advanced radar and sensing systems is critical to realizing their potential in many areas.

At its core, sensing is the process of collecting data or information about the environment using various techniques. It involves the use of specialized sensors, advanced signal processing algorithms and precise measurement methods to extract meaningful insights from the data received. Sensing systems are designed to capture and interpret signals or waves propagating through the medium under investigation⁵⁸.

⁵⁸ HardwareBee, “The Ultimate Guide to Radar Sensor - HardwareBee.” <https://hardwarebee.com/the-ultimate-guide-to-radar-sensor/>.

This section explores the state of the art in the field of radar and sensing systems. It will review radar systems and their classification, describing the main capabilities for information estimation and detailing the main parameters to be considered when designing a radar system. Next, the concept of joint communications and sensing is introduced, as well as the main approaches to integrate a radar system with a communications system. To conclude this section, the main issues to be considered when integrating a sensing system in the use case proposed in this document will be detailed.

7.1.1 Radar systems and general classification

Radar systems play a crucial role in modern technology, enabling the detection and tracking of objects at various distances and in different environmental conditions. These systems have revolutionized many industries, including aviation, meteorology, and defense.

Radar, an acronym for "Radio Detection and Ranging", uses the principle of electromagnetic waves to detect and locate objects in their environment. By emitting radio waves and analyzing the signals reflected by targets, radar systems can determine the range, speed, direction, etc. of objects with remarkable accuracy, providing vital information for navigation, weather monitoring, air traffic control and military surveillance. To understand the wide variety of radar systems in use today, it is important to examine their general classification. The main classifications of radar systems and their principles and functions are categorized based on number of antennas, their operations, type of modulation, purpose of use, according to the operating frequency, and its application as follows.

7.1.1.1 According to the number of antennas

- Mono-static: A single device transmits and receives.
- Bi-static: One device transmits, and another receives, at the same or different locations.
- Multistatic: Combines the information received by several devices.

7.1.1.2 According to the operation

- Primary: Operates independently of the target, depending only on the RCS of the target.
- Secondary: The radar interrogates the target, which responds, normally with a series of data (height of the aircraft, etc.). In the case of military vehicles, the friend-or-foe identifier is included.

7.1.1.3 According to type of modulation

- Continuous Wave (CW) Radar: Transmits uninterrupted, usually with some form of modulation that allows determination of when the signal corresponding to an echo was transmitted. Police radar is usually continuous wave and Doppler effect.
- Pulsed Wave Radar: This is the usual operation. A pulse is transmitted, which may or may not be modulated, and the radar waits to receive its echo before launching the next pulse. If echoes of pulses prior to the last one transmitted appear, they will be interpreted as belonging to the latter, so that traces of non-existent targets will appear.

7.1.1.4 According to purpose of use

- **Tracking radar:** Capable of tracking the movement of a target. For example, missile guidance radar.
- **Search radar:** Scans the whole space, or a sector of it, showing all targets that appear. There are radars capable of operating in both modes.

7.1.1.5 According to frequency

IEEE Band Designation	Frequency Range	Typical Usage and Characteristics
HF	3-30 MHz	Over the horizon surveillance; <i>low range and low resolution</i>
VHF	50-330 MHz	Long range (Line of Sight) surveillance, Foliage penetration (FOPEN), counter-stealth, ground penetrating; <i>low/medium resolution</i>
UHF	300-1000 MHz	Long range surveillance, FOPEN; <i>low/medium resolution</i>
L	1-2 GHz	Long range surveillance, Long-range air traffic control; <i>medium resolution and small weather effects</i>
S	2-4 GHz	Moderate-range surveillance, terminal air traffic control, long-range weather observation, airborne early warning (AEW); <i>moderate weather effect in heavy precipitation</i>
C	4-8 GHz	Long-range tracking, weather observation, weapon location; <i>increased weather effect in light/medium rain</i>
X	8-12 GHz	Short-range tracking, missile guidance, mapping marine radar, airborne intercept, battlefield surveillance, weapon location; <i>reduce to short range operation in rain</i>
Ku	12-18 GHz	High-resolution mapping, satellite altimetry, man-portable/unmanned air vehicle (UAV) radar; <i>short range due to water vapor absorption</i>
K	18-27 GHz	Police radar; <i>very limited use due to high water vapor absorption</i>
Ka	27-40 GHz	Short-range very high-resolution mapping, airport surveillance; <i>short range due to water vapor absorption</i>
V	40-75 GHz	Scientific remote sensing; <i>high water vapor absorption</i>
W	75-110 GHz	Automobile cruise control (77 GHz), missile seekers, very high-resolution imaging (94 GHz); <i>high water vapor absorption elsewhere in the band</i>
Mm	110-300 GHz	Experimental; <i>limited to short range due to high water vapor absorption</i>

Table 7.1.1.5. Radar frequency bands and its typical usage⁵⁹.

7.1.1.6 According to the application

Military equipment:

- Air defense: recognition, aircraft navigation, missile guidance.
- Battlefield radar: recognition, navigation, weapon guidance, aiming control radar.
- Air traffic control (also for civilian applications): route radar, airfield surveillance, precision approach radar, surface radar, meteo radar.

Civilian equipment:

- Industrial: meteo radar, surveillance, security, material testing, research.

7.1.2 Radar main estimation capabilities

Accurate estimation of key parameters is critical in radar technology, enabling valuable information to be extracted from the environment. Radar systems are designed to transmit and receive electromagnetic signals, enabling them to detect, track and analyze targets in a wide

⁵⁹ N. Ismail, T. Surya Gunawan, S. Kartika S, T. Praludi, and E. A.Z. Hamidi, "Design of microstrip hairpin bandpass filter for 2.9 GHz – 3.1 GHz s-band radar with defected ground structure," Malaysian J. Fundam. Appl. Sci., vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 448–455, 2019, doi: 10.11113/mjfas.v14n4.1073.

range of applications. In this subsection, we will explore the essential radar estimation capabilities that enable these systems to provide accurate measurements and insights.

The estimation capabilities of radar systems are decisive to understanding the characteristics and behavior of targets. These capabilities cover a range of parameters including range, velocity and angle. Using advanced signal processing techniques and mathematical algorithms, radar systems can derive accurate and reliable estimations, enabling a deeper understanding of targets and their interactions with the environment⁶⁰.

- **Range Estimation:** One of the primary capabilities of radar systems is range estimation, which determines the distance between the radar and the target. Range estimation is based on the time it takes for the radar signal to travel to the target and return to the radar. By measuring the time delay between the transmitted and received signals, the radar can accurately calculate the range. This capability is crucial for tracking and locating targets in various applications, including surveillance, navigation, and military operations.
- **Bistatic Range Estimation:** In addition to monostatic radar systems, which use the same antenna for transmission and reception, radar systems can also employ bistatic configurations. Bistatic radar systems separate the transmitting and receiving antennas, which introduces additional challenges but offers unique advantages. Bistatic range estimation involves calculating the target range using the time delay between the transmitted signal from the transmitter and the received signal at the receiver. This capability expands the radar's coverage and enhances its ability to detect and track targets in complex scenarios.
- **Velocity Estimation:** Radar systems can estimate the velocity of a target by measuring the Doppler shift in the received signal. The Doppler effect results in a shift in frequency when the radar signal reflects off a moving target. By analyzing this frequency shift, the radar can determine the target's radial velocity relative to the radar. Velocity estimation is essential for detecting moving targets, such as vehicles or aircraft, and can be used in applications like traffic control, weather monitoring, and air traffic control.
- **Angle Estimation:** Radar systems equipped with multiple or moving antennas can estimate the angle of arrival (AOA) of a target. By analyzing the phase or time differences between the signals received by the antennas, the radar can determine the direction from which the target is approaching. Angle estimation provides valuable information about the target's position in relation to the radar and is used in various applications, including target tracking, surveillance, and direction finding.
 - **Multiantenna Angle Estimation:** Radar systems with multiple antennas can utilize advanced signal processing techniques to estimate the angle of arrival

⁶⁰ M. Weiß, "Radar Fundamentals. More Basics and Statistical Signal Processing," Int. Summer Sch. Radar/SAR, 2018.

with improved accuracy. These techniques, such as beamforming and spatial filtering, exploit the spatial characteristics of the received signals to enhance angle estimation. Multiantenna angle estimation enables the radar to accurately locate and track targets even in challenging environments with clutter, interference, or multiple targets.

- **Moving Antenna Angle Estimation:** Radar systems that incorporate moving antennas, such as phased array radars, can perform angle estimation by steering the antenna beam electronically. By controlling the beam direction, the radar can determine the angle at which the target is located. Moving antenna angle estimation allows for rapid scanning of the surveillance area and enables the radar to track multiple targets simultaneously.

Overall, the radar estimation capabilities of range, velocity and angle form the backbone of radar systems, enabling them to provide valuable insights and measurements in a wide range of applications. By exploiting these capabilities, radar technology continues to advance and contribute to critical areas, ensuring improved safety, security, and efficiency in various industries.

7.1.3 Radar design criteria

The successful design and implementation of radar systems depends on a comprehensive understanding of several key factors. In this sub-section four critical aspects of radar design are presented: frequency, bandwidth, power and duty cycle. Each of these factors plays a crucial role in determining the overall performance and capabilities of a radar system. By examining the considerations and trade-offs associated with these design criteria, engineers can develop radar systems that meet specific requirements and deliver optimal results in a range of applications³.

- **Frequency:** The choice of frequency is a crucial factor in radar design, as it directly impacts the system's performance and operational characteristics. The selection of frequency depends on the specific application requirements and environmental conditions. Lower frequencies, such as S-band (2-4 GHz) or L-band (1-2 GHz), provide better penetration through obstacles like vegetation or buildings, making them suitable for ground surveillance radars. On the other hand, higher frequencies, like X-band (8-12 GHz) or Ku-band (12-18 GHz), offer improved resolution and accuracy, making them ideal for precision tracking or weather radar systems.
- **Bandwidth:** The bandwidth of a radar system determines its range resolution and target detection capabilities. A wider bandwidth allows for better range resolution, enabling the radar to distinguish between closely spaced targets. The required bandwidth depends on the desired range resolution and target characteristics. For instance, in high-resolution imaging radars, wide bandwidths are essential to achieve fine detail in the radar image. The bandwidth also influences the radar's ability to detect targets with different velocities or Doppler shifts.

- **Power:** The power level of a radar system plays a significant role in determining its detection range and sensitivity. Higher transmit power provides a longer detection range and improves the radar's ability to detect weak or distant targets. However, increased power consumption and system complexity are trade-offs that must be considered. The power requirements depend on factors such as the desired maximum range, target size, desired signal-to-noise ratio, and clutter conditions. It is crucial to strike a balance between power consumption, system size, and the desired operational capabilities of the radar.
- **Duty Cycle:** The duty cycle represents the ratio of active transmission time to the total time interval of a radar system. It directly influences the radar's average power consumption and its ability to detect targets within a given time frame. The duty cycle is typically optimized to ensure efficient use of power and to mitigate issues like overheating or excessive transmitter wear. For example, surveillance radars may employ low-duty cycle operation, where the transmitter is active for only a fraction of the total time, conserving power while still maintaining sufficient target detection capability. On the other hand, tracking radars may require continuous or high-duty cycle operation for real-time target updates.

In summary, the design criteria for radar systems encompass several key parameters. The choice of frequency determines the radar's operational characteristics, while bandwidth influences range resolution and target detection capabilities. Power considerations are vital to achieve the desired detection range and sensitivity while managing power consumption. The duty cycle plays a role in efficient system operation and target tracking performance. Consideration of these criteria is essential to design radar systems that meet the desired performance goals.

7.1.4 Radar representation

Radar representation holds significant importance in radar systems and applications. It provides a visual depiction of the radar data, allowing operators to analyze and interpret the information gathered by the radar system quickly and effectively. By presenting radar data in a structured and intuitive manner, radar representation aids in target detection, tracking, and identification, as well as in assessing the overall performance of the radar system⁶¹.

As a radar visualization technique, Range-Doppler maps (see Fig.4) offer a powerful means to represent and analyze the range and velocity information obtained by radar systems. By transforming radar signals into a two-dimensional map, they provide a comprehensive and intuitive visualization of the spatial and velocity distribution of targets within the radar's coverage area.

⁶¹ D. Tahmoush and J. Silvius, "Time-integrated range-Doppler maps for visualizing and classifying radar data," IEEE Natl. Radar Conf. - Proc., pp. 372–374, 2011, doi: 10.1109/RADAR.2011.5960562.

Figure 7.1.4.1. The basic process of generating the RD map⁶²

The Range-Doppler map provides a visual representation of the range and velocity distribution of targets within the radar's coverage area. It allows operators to observe the spatial extent of targets along the range axis and their relative velocities along the Doppler axis. The Doppler frequency axis represents the relative radial velocity of the targets. Positive Doppler frequencies correspond to targets moving away from the radar, while negative frequencies indicate targets moving towards the radar. The intensity of each point in the map represents the strength of the Doppler return from the target at the corresponding range and frequency.

⁶² T. Jeong and S. Lee, "Resource-Efficient Range-Doppler Map Generation Using Deep Learning Network for Automotive Radar Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, no. May, pp. 55965–55977, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3282688.

Figure 7.1.4.2. Range Doppler Matrix: As the target moves towards the radar, it induces a positive Doppler shift⁶³.

By analyzing the Range-Doppler map, radar operators can identify and track moving targets, detect stationary objects, distinguish between clutter and actual targets, and assess the overall radar system performance.

7.1.5 Joint Communication and Sensing approaches

Wireless communications and radar (C&R) are two closely related fields that have evolved in parallel for several years. They share common features in terms of signal processing algorithms, devices and, to some extent, system architecture. They also have the possibility to share a spectrum. This has motivated a lot of research interest in the coexistence, cooperation, and joint design (or co-design) of the two systems. The coexistence of C&R systems has been a major research topic in the last decade, with a focus on developing efficient interference management techniques so that the two systems can operate smoothly without interfering with each other. Even though C&R systems may be co-located and even physically integrated, they transmit two different signals that overlap in the time and/or frequency domain⁶⁴.

The co-design of collocated communication and radar (C&R) systems involves combining these two functions into a single system. There is currently a growing interest in this joint

⁶³ T. Jeong and S. Lee, "Resource-Efficient Range-Doppler Map Generation Using Deep Learning Network for Automotive Radar Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, no. May, pp. 55965–55977, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3282688.

⁶⁴ Andrew Zhang, J., Member, S., Liu, F., Masouros, C., Heath Jr, R. W., Feng, Z., Zheng, L., & Petropulu, A. (n.d.). *An Overview of Signal Processing Techniques for Joint Communication and Radar Sensing*.

system from both academic and industrial sectors. It has shown tremendous potential in various fields, including emerging defense applications and, more recently, in Smart Cities applications such as intelligent vehicular networks and the Internet of Things (IoT). By integrating communication and radar functionalities into a single system, it becomes possible to address challenges associated with congested sensors and transceivers. This integration offers several benefits, including reduced device size, power consumption, and cost. Moreover, it enables more efficient utilization of the radio spectrum and is expected to significantly enhance the capabilities and performance of both communication and radar sensing⁶⁵.

There are three main approaches to designing systems that can perform both communication and radar functions:

- **Communication-centric design:** This approach prioritizes the communication aspect of the system and uses the same waveform to obtain radar information from the target echoes. This requires some modifications to the hardware and algorithms to enable radar sensing capabilities. Additionally, some changes to the communication standards may be needed to improve the radar performance. The advantage of this approach is that it preserves the communication quality, but the drawback is that the radar performance may vary depending on the scenario and may be hard to adjust.
- **Radar-centric design:** This approach focuses on the radar aspect of the system and embeds information signaling in the existing radar waveform. This ensures a high-quality radar performance but limits the data rates that can be achieved by the communication function. The trade-off of this approach is that some radar performance may be sacrificed to allow for better communication quality.
- **Joint design and optimization:** This approach considers both communication and radar aspects from the beginning and designs a system that can balance the trade-off between them. This allows for a flexible and adaptable system that can adjust its performance according to the needs and constraints of each function. The challenge of this approach is to find an optimal solution that satisfies both communication and radar requirements.

The primary challenge in designing C&R systems that belong to the first two categories is to enable the secondary functionality without degrading the performance of the primary system. This requires careful consideration of the signal formats and protocols of the primary system, and how to embed or modify them to achieve the desired C&R objectives. On the other hand, C&R systems in the third category have more flexibility in choosing the signal waveform, system configuration, and network architecture, as they are jointly optimized for both C&R purposes. This allows for a tunable tradeoff between C&R performance metrics, depending on the application scenarios and requirements. In scenarios where a good communication system is critical for proper operation and radar measurements are an addition/enhancement, it makes

⁶⁵ Mealey, R. M. (1963). A Method for Calculating Error Probabilities in a Radar Communication System. *IEEE Transactions on Space Electronics and Telemetry*, 9(2), 37–42. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSET.1963.4337601>

more sense to decide to use a communication-centric scheme. This approach offers several advantages over the radar-centric and joint design and optimization approaches, especially when addressing critical parameters for sub-THz communication with very high-rate requirements.

Although the radar-centric approach may be well-suited for applications focused primarily on radar functionalities, its limitations in terms of data rate, spectrum efficiency, interference mitigation, cost, complexity make it less favorable in the context of realizing a system that combines both communication and radar capabilities. On the other hand, while the joint design and optimization approach may offer certain benefits by considering the specific requirements of both communication and radar, it can be challenging to strike a balance between the conflicting objectives of the two domains.

The communication-centric approach, on the other hand, places a clear emphasis on meeting the critical parameters for sub-THz communication, such as high data rates, spectrum efficiency, future compatibility, etc. By doing so, it optimizes the system's performance and ensures the realization of a robust, high-rate sub-THz communication system that effectively incorporates radar functionalities.

7.1.6 Communications-based sensing

As mentioned in the previous section, JCAS communication-centric systems are one of the best options for integrating sensing capabilities into a communication system, especially when it requires very stable communication with high data rate and bandwidth. In the proposed use cases this is critical, therefore, from this point onwards the analysis will focus on this type of approach to joint communications and sensing. This section summarizes some of the key concepts to consider for a communication centric JCAS system.

- **Passive radar.** For this type of JCAS approach, passive radar is a very suitable option to carry out this integration. Passive radar is one of the key techniques in communication centric JCAS. Passive radar utilizes existing radio frequency (RF) signals, such as broadcast, cellular, or satellite transmissions, as the illuminators of opportunity. Instead of transmitting its own signals, passive radar exploits the reflections of these signals from targets of interest. By analyzing the changes in the received signal, it is possible to detect, track, and classify targets without requiring dedicated radar transmitters. Passive radar offers advantages such as reduced cost, covert operation, and the ability to leverage existing infrastructure for sensing purposes.
- **Sensing systems in different frequency bands.** Detection systems in different frequency bands play a critical role in communication centric JCAS applications. These systems exploit the unique characteristics of different frequency bands to achieve specific detection objectives. Lower frequency bands provide excellent penetration capabilities, microwave bands balance resolution and penetration, millimeter-wave and terahertz bands provide high-resolution sensing, UV and IR bands capture detailed environmental information, and multi-band and multispectral approaches combine the strengths of different frequency bands to enhance sensing capabilities. By exploiting

the unique characteristics of different frequency bands, communication centric JCAS systems can perform a wide range of sensing tasks with improved accuracy and efficiency⁶⁶.

- **Ambiguity function.** In the context of communication centric JCAS, the ambiguity function refers to a mathematical representation used to analyze and characterize the performance of a radar system. The ambiguity function describes the time and frequency response of a system to a transmitted signal and its correlation with delayed and frequency-shifted versions of itself. The ambiguity function is often represented as a two-dimensional function, with time delay on one axis and Doppler shift on the other. The shape and characteristics of the ambiguity function can provide valuable insights into the system's performance and limitations.
- **IEEE 802.11bf standard.** 802.11bf, also known as Wi-Fi sensing, is an emerging standard within the IEEE 802.11 family that enables communication centric JCAS applications. This standard allows Wi-Fi devices to leverage the existing Wi-Fi infrastructure for sensing purposes. By analyzing changes in the wireless channel characteristics, such as the channel state information (CSI), Wi-Fi devices can perform tasks like motion detection, gesture recognition, and human tracking. The availability of CSI allows for advanced signal processing techniques, including beamforming, target localization, and spatial mapping. 802.11bf expands the capabilities of Wi-Fi devices beyond traditional communication and enables them to act as radar-like sensors⁶⁷. This IEEE 802.11bf standard for WLAN and Integrated Sensing is one of the leading initiatives of JCAS systems, which will help to increase research and standardization of other Joint Communication and Sensing systems.
- **Multicarrier versus Single carrier.** In communication centric JCAS, the choice between multicarrier and monocarrier techniques depends on various factors. Multicarrier modulation schemes, such as OFDM, divide the available spectrum into multiple subcarriers. This division enables efficient transmission and improved robustness against frequency-selective fading. Multicarrier techniques are beneficial when dealing with multipath propagation and can provide better resilience in challenging environments. On the other hand, monocarrier techniques use a single carrier waveform for both communication and sensing tasks. Monocarrier systems may be simpler to implement and require less computational resources. The choice between multicarrier and monocarrier depends on factors such as system complexity, available bandwidth, channel characteristics, and the specific requirements of the application.
- **OFDM radar / OFDM for JCAS.** OFDM is a modulation scheme widely used in modern communication systems, including Wi-Fi, 4G LTE, and 5G. It divides the available spectrum into multiple orthogonal subcarriers, which are closely spaced in the frequency domain. By transmitting data simultaneously across these subcarriers, OFDM enables efficient spectrum utilization and robustness against frequency-selective fading caused by multipath propagation.

⁶⁶ M. Parker, "Radar Basics," Digit. Signal Process. 101, pp. 231–240, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-811453-7.00018-4.

⁶⁷ R. Du et al., "An Overview on IEEE 802.11bf: WLAN Sensing," 2022.

Recently, the concept of data transmission via OFDM radar has gained significant attention in the field. It has emerged as one of the most prominent and widely discussed scientific topics in the present day. This innovative approach allows for embedded communication within radars, facilitating resource sharing between sensing and communication tasks. Within this domain, a crucial objective is to examine the impact of data transmission on the radar system's traditional capabilities and propose methods for enhancing its performance⁶⁸.

The ability to transmit data proves particularly advantageous in Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems. By employing OFDM, multistatic systems with passive location and alternative processing methods, instead of the conventional matched filter, can be established. Nevertheless, it is essential to analyze the time-frequency characteristics of radar signals generated using OFDM. As a result of advancements in hardware capabilities and the growing demands on the RF spectrum, the utilization of OFDM implementations in radar is expected to continue expanding in popularity. Furthermore, it has been shown that OFDM-like signals are also suitable for radar applications. Also, it has already been proposed in literature to implement radar networks with integrated communications functions based on OFDM signals⁶⁹.

In conclusion, OFDM radar combines the advantages of OFDM communication with radar principles, enabling communication centric JCAS systems to perform simultaneous communication and sensing tasks. The joint exploitation of radar and communication functionalities, high range resolution, robustness to multipath interference, and efficient spectrum utilization make OFDM radar an attractive choice for various applications.

- **Preamble versus Complete waveform.** In communication centric JCAS, the decision to use a preamble or the full waveform depends on several factors, including the specific application requirements, available transmitted signal information, desired accuracy, and the trade-off between sensing performance and communication efficiency. The preamble is a segment of a transmitted signal used for synchronization, channel estimation, and initial processing. It consists of a known sequence of symbols inserted at the beginning of the transmission. Using a preamble is particularly useful when computational resources are limited or when rapid processing is necessary. It simplifies the estimation process, enabling efficient sensing with reduced complexity.

On the other hand, using the full waveform involves utilizing the entire transmitted signal, including both the preamble and data part (maybe previously known data), for sensing tasks. This approach provides access to more information beyond synchronization and channel estimation, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis

⁶⁸ M. Kniola, A. Kawalec Michal Kniola, A. Kawalec, and M. Kniola, "Properties of chosen OFDM-generated radar waveforms," <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2565235>, vol. 11442, no. 11, pp. 84–90, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1117/12.2565235.

⁶⁹ C. Sturm, T. Zwick, and W. Wiesbeck, "An OFDM system concept for joint radar and communications operations," *IEEE Veh. Technol. Conf.*, no. 4, pp. 0–4, 2009, doi: 10.1109/VETECS.2009.5073387.

of the received signal. The advantages of using the full waveform include increased accuracy in sensing tasks, as it provides detailed information about the transmitted signal and its characteristics. This leads to improved target detection, classification, and parameter estimation. Additionally, analyzing the full waveform enables estimation of the average power of the transmitted signal, which is valuable for certain sensing applications. However, using the full waveform requires more complex algorithms and can result in higher computational overhead compared to using just the preamble.

7.2 High level design

The high-level design of this sub-THz JCAS system focuses on the integration of communication and sensing capabilities in a passive radar framework. Using sub-THz technologies, this communication-centric system employs the OFDM multicarrier waveform to enable efficient communication and sensing functionalities. This section highlights the motivation for adopting a passive radar approach and justifies the use of the OFDM multicarrier waveform in the JCAS system.

This system uses a passive radar concept, which allows it to use existing communication signals as illuminators for sensing purposes. Unlike active radar systems, which require dedicated transmitters, passive radar uses ambient signals, such as broadcast or communication signals, to perform sensing tasks. By using the received signals of opportunity, the JCAS system can extract valuable information about the environment without transmitting an additional signal. This passive sensing approach offers several advantages, including reduced power consumption, reduced cost and reduced integration complexity into a pre-defined system, such as the Extended Reality scenario.

The use of OFDM multicarrier waveform in the JCAS system for sub-THz technologies is a justified decision due to several reasons. Firstly, OFDM provides high spectral efficiency by dividing the available bandwidth into subcarriers, allowing simultaneous transmission and efficient utilization of the wide spectrum available in sub-THz frequency bands. This maximizes data rates for communication purposes.

OFDM has gained significant popularity and widespread adoption not only in communication systems but also in radar scenarios. Its well-established presence in communication standards such as Wi-Fi and 4G/5G cellular networks has led to extensive research and development, making OFDM a well-known and mature waveform. This familiarity and knowledge have been leveraged to extend the use of OFDM in radar applications. By capitalizing on its inherent advantages, such as spectral efficiency, robustness to channel variations, and the ability to exploit frequency diversity, OFDM has demonstrated promising results in radar systems. The utilization of OFDM in radar scenarios brings the advantages of a mature waveform, offering improved performance and reliability for sensing and target detection in a wide range of environments.

Three alternatives, listed in increasing level of complexity, are proposed to perform the sensing operations. These options will be evaluated to decide which one is best suited to this use case.

- **Spectrum Use Adaptation:** The system can switch between communication and sensing modes based on a previously defined criterion.
- **Full Waveform Sensing with Known Data:** In this approach, the system utilizes the entire OFDM multicarrier waveform, including the known data, for sensing purposes. By analyzing the received waveform, the system can extract target information such as range, velocity, and angle of arrival with better accuracy. This alternative reduces the effective data rate due to the need to use a known payload without useful information for communication.
- **Preamble-Based Sensing:** In this case, the system utilizes a dedicated preamble within the OFDM multicarrier waveform for sensing purposes. The preamble contains known data patterns that allow the system to extract range and velocity information from the received signals. This method provides accurate sensing capabilities while preserving the primary communication waveform for data transmission.

8 General description of the XR scenario

The targeted scenario consists of several rooms, each room equipped with 3 Kinect cameras and a capture system (in a PC) that collects the data flows from the cameras. There are several users per room wearing HMD devices. The UL is the connection towards the rendering system (here depicted as a router) and the DL represents the connection from the rendering system to the HMD. The flow transmitted from each capture system is processed and “merged” with flows from other rooms and the resulting composed video stream is sent to each HMD (system DL). The following figure represents this scenario, where capture system flows are differentiated by colors, and the composed video stream would be the DL flows.

Figure 8.1. XR System.

Some additional characteristics of the system are:

- The UL video flow is 6 Mbps, though a 5x increase is under study.
- A PC in each room generates a 3D reconstruction of the person in the room.

Two use cases (Fig.7) are considered for the deployment of the sub-THz link. The difference between them is whether the processing is done either on a PC or on the Edge. The sub-THz link can supply connectivity where it is indicated by the red arrows in the diagram. For this purpose, none of the schemes poses any advantage or drawback and they are very similar. However, the final decision may be conditioned by the type of connectivity, connectors and interfaces at the end of the red lines, as the market of sub-THz hardware is limited. In that sense, we would require the specification of the potential interfaces as detailed as possible. For the sake of completeness, the diagrams presented in the meeting of June 8, 2023 are included, in which i2CAT posed the utilization of the sub-THz link for the UL and DL (Fig.8).

Figure 7. Use cases proposed by i2CAT

Figure 8.2. Options for the sub-THz link in use case 2 proposed by i2CAT

9 The sub-THz link in the XR scenario

The sub-THz link will follow the structure shown in the diagram of Fig.1 and will convey incoming IP flow between the two ends. This approach allows the development of the sub-THz link for any of the 3 options shown in the next two sections, as long as an IP flow over Ethernet is delivered to the incoming point.

Target demonstration: real video flow generated by i2CAT, depending on in which part of the network the sub-THz link is placed (e.g. the capture system). However, Gradient’s experience dealing with this type of signals shows that unexpected integration issues such as fragmentation incompatibilities can provoke a long delay in the implementation. In that case, as soon as we detect that the real video flow cannot be integrated within the expected time, an alternative synthetic video flow can replace the first option to test the correct performance of the sub-THz link.

Figure 9.1. Sub-THz link

9.1 Sub-THz link for the UL

In the UL there exist two possibilities, analyzed for the use case 2: i) the sub-THz link is placed between the Lightwave PC and the access point (AP); ii) the sub-THz link is placed between one Kinect camera and the capture system.

9.1.1 Sub-THz link between Lightwave PC and the AP

In this case, the link would transport the flow after the processing performed by the capture system (that collects the signals coming from the Kinect cameras) and the Lightwave PC to the AP. The sensing system (at the AP end) would detect objects between the Lightwave PC and the AP that can potentially disrupt the line of sight (LOS) between transmitter and receiver.

9.1.2 Sub-THz link between Kinect camera and capture system.

In this case, the link would transport the flow corresponding to one Kinect camera to the capture system. The sensing system (at the capture system end) would detect objects between the Kinect camera and the capture system. In a future evolution, a system configuration with 3 cameras connected via a sub-THz link enables user localization.

9.2 Sub-THz link for the DL

The main difference with respect to the utilization of the sub-THz link for the UL is that the detection (sensing) functionality is, in this case, located at the user (HMD) side. From the sensing point of view, the receiver (a person wearing the HMD) is moving and the system can be used to detect obstacles in the user's trajectory.

10 Conclusion

In the light of the previous analysis, the option of 3-(ii) poses uncertainties that may impact the development of the project, such as the proprietary interfaces. On the other hand, this option is the one that offers the lowest efficiency, as only one flow (we assume much lower than 6 Mbps) employs a link of potentially 2 Gbps.

Regarding options 3-(i) and 4, their efficiency performance is higher, as the data rate is 6 Mbps and $6(N - 1)$ Mbps, respectively. From the sensing perspective, the DL scenario (option of section 4) is more interesting as it provides the possibility of exploring the interaction of a moving receiver with the environment, while the receiver in 3-(i) is static.

A first analysis shows that the utilization of the sub-THz link for the DL is the more viable and interesting use case. This analysis does not include the congestion issues mentioned in previous discussions, that can be incorporated in subsequent versions of this document. From a further discussion between i2CAT and Gradiant hold on July 4, both institutions agreed to select as use case the utilization of the **sub-THz link for the UL between the Lightware PC and the access point (AP)** described in 7.1 as it makes it possible to detect a user on the room between these two endpoints.